

THE ROLE OF NARRATIVE TWIST TECHNIQUE IN THE STRUCTURE OF THE SHORT STORY GENRE

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20151762>

Annotation: In literary studies, the genre of the short story has always been in the spotlight due to its convenient form and profound content. The complexity of the short story genre relies in its ability to deliver immense significance through a "Narrative twist", turning a brief moment into a powerful psychological impact. This article analyzes the specific features of the short story genre, in particular the structural and psychological power of the narrative twist technique. Furthermore, this research highlights the history of the short story and how authors modify the result the reader expectations, as well as the influence of readers on this process. This article references the compositions of Roald Dahl and Muratbay Nizanov to clarify specifically.

Key words: short story, narrative twist, genre, Dahl, Nizanov, climax, denouement.

Story (from Persian – "to talk" and "to converse") - is fiction of such briefness that is not able to support any subplots. [2, p. 42] A story usually depicts a single event from a hero's life. [5:393] In the 19th century, the story genre reached its peak of development in Europe. The main feature of this genre is that, despite the small size of the story, it must cause a strong emotional impact on the reader. The authors commence to employ the "narrative twist" technique to manage the stories' plot and keep the reader excited until the end. During the research to demonstrate the application of this technique in various directions, we employ the works of Roald Dahl and Muratbay Nizanov who are well-known figures of short story genre. Dahl uses an unexpected conclusion for psychological excitement, while Nizanov uses it as a sharp tool for social satire.

In the short story genre, narrative twist is not just a twist, but the central mechanism that sets the story in motion. Its main role is to reconstruct the logical connection between climax and denouement.

The climax is the top-most point of the story turning over the truth that the reader expects. That is, the fact that the author leads the reader in one direction and changes the direction by 180 degrees at the highest point and the author increases exponentially the emotional power of the work. [2, p. 55]

Moreover, the climax is immediately followed by a denouement. At this stage, all questions are answered and logically concluded. The situation that takes shape as a result of the development of the entire preceding action to clarify specifically, Roald Dahl's "The Great Automatic Grammatizator" illustrates how a narrative twist can redefine the entire meaning of a story.

In this story Dahl skillfully employs foreshadowing through the character of Adolph Knipe. While Mr. Bohlen celebrates the machine as a mathematical success, Knipe's melancholy

face and his nervous fiddling with a paper clip suggest a hidden, more complex agenda. This creates a subtle tension; the reader expects a story about engineering, but the narrative twist later reveals that the machine is designed to mechanize human creativity itself. By focusing on these minute psychological details, Dahl prepares the structural ground for a climax that completely shatters the reader's initial perception of the invention."

The narrative twist technique of the story is not just a plot, but a powerful influence on the reader's psyche. Specifically, the reader creates the development of events in their mind while reading the story. When a twist occurs, the student falls into a state of shock, and the brain immediately begins to process information and accept the new reality. As an example, we mention, Muratbay Nizanov's story "Kúilmegen sawǵa", the narrative twist functions as a moral mirror. For instance, in his satirical works, the climax often reveals a character's true hypocrisy or a hidden social reality. This creates a psychological impact where the reader moves from satire to deep reflection.

— *Oqı! — dedi soń buyırıp.*

Men hayran bolıp júzine tigildim.

— *Oqı dep atırman sizge!*

Áste konvertti ashtım. Otkritkadaǵı qosıqqa kózim túskeni sol, júregim toqtap qalayın dedi.

[3, p. 231]

Sonda barıp abayladım, sawǵalardı bir kún burın xatker qızdıń shkafına salıp ketken edik. Meniń kúilmegen sawǵam oǵan jaqqay qalıp, baslıqtiki menen almastırıp qoyǵan eken. [3, p. 232]

In this story, Muratbay Nizanov deftly used narrative twist. In the course of events, the hero believes that his poem pleased the boss. The reader will assume that the hero himself erroneously changed the poems. However, the story ends completely unexpectedly. At the climax, it turns out that the third person, the secretary, whom no one expected, deliberately interchanged the poems. This turn dramatically increases the emotional power of the work. Although the story is rich in humorous events, behind this laughter lies the negative behavior of the characters, in particular, the secretary girl, and the complexity of human relationships in society. This awakens in the reader not just pleasure, but a deep psychological and socially critical view.

In conclusion, the narrative twist is not merely a plot device but forms the structural foundation of the short story genre. The comparative analysis of the works of Roald Dahl and Muratbay Nizanov demonstrates that the narrative twist technique has a psychological impact on the reader, raises the story to a more intense point, and gives pleasure to occurrence of an unexpected event. The main tool that elevates the story to the level of true art is narrative twist.

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